

Founding, Running, and Improving Scholarly Journals

A compendium of resources

This non-exhaustive compendium of resources on founding, running, and improving scholarly journals was created by Andrea Blatz (University of Texas Press) and Mario Pallua (Libertas International University) as part of a poster presentation at the Society for Scholarly Publishing (SSP) annual conference in Portland Oregon in May 2023.

The items in the compendium were added based on suggestions by our interviewees, responses to our questionnaire, and independent research. This compendium does not aim to be an exhaustive list, but rather a good starting point for someone wishing to expand their knowledge of the existing resources available.

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1. Websites

[University of Kansas Libraries Guide](#) is a detailed guide to assist those thinking of starting a new journal or working with an existing journal.

McGill University's [Scholarly Journal Publishing Guide](#) is an overview of the major considerations for scholarly journals and includes templates, sample statements, and recommendations for best practices.

[University of Michigan's Publishing Wiki](#) provides documentation of different parts of journal publishing.

The [OA Journals Toolkit](#) is being built as a community-led initiative funded by OASPA and DOAJ, aiming to support new and established OA journals in navigating the rapidly changing landscape of OA publishing.

[The PLACE](#) is the Publishers Learning and Community Exchange, an online forum started by COPE.

[Start a New Publication with ACM](#) is one example of a society's new journal guidelines.

2. Books

[The Science Editors' Handbook](#) (2013) published by the European Society for Scholarly Publishing (EASE) features 56 chapters written by 40 international authors with experience in all areas of science editing and publishing. It covers a wide range of subjects, including all aspects

of copy editing and running a journal and provides examples of good practice, plus hints and tips that can help to solve problems and support good decisions.

[The Handbook of Journal Publishing](#) (2013) published by Cambridge University Press is a comprehensive reference work written by experienced professionals, covering all aspects of journal publishing, both online and in print.

[The Oxford Handbook of Publishing](#) (2019) published by Oxford University Press (OUP) surveys publishing in all of its great diversity.

[A Pocket Guide to Academic Publishing](#) (2017) published by the University of the Arctic is a short guide to academic publishing written in plain language.

[Hrvatski znanstveni časopisi](#) (2015) published by the Croatian Association of Scholarly Editors (ZNAK) and written in Croatian is in part an analysis of Croatian journals and in part a guide on publishing scholarly journals.

[Writing Successfully in Science](#) (2002), [How to copyedit scientific books & journals](#) (1986), [Writing scientific papers in English: An ELSE-Ciba Foundation guide for authors](#) (1975), and [Editing scientific books and journals: An ELSE-Ciba Foundation guide for editors](#) (1978) are books written by Maeve O'Connor.

[Creating an Undergraduate Literary Journal: A Production Guide for Students and Faculty](#) (2022) published by Bloomsbury Academic and authored by Audrey Colombe provides a wealth of information for faculty advisors, student and faculty editors, and undergraduates and graduate students alike on the business of literary publishing and tips for building, developing, expanding, and marketing a successful literary magazine.

[Becoming a Scholarly Journal Editor: Practical Advice for Editors and Tips for Authors](#) (2022) published by Rowman & Littlefield Publishers and authored by Wayne Journell is intended to be a guide for scholarly journal editors. It walks current and prospective editors through the various steps of the editing process, including establishing an editorial vision, creating editorial teams/boards, interpreting reviewers' comments and writing decision letters, and publicizing published articles and improving journal metrics.

[Developing Open Access Journals: A Practical Guide](#) (2008) is a book authored by David J. Solomon and published by Chandos Publishing and is a practical guide to developing and maintaining an electronic open access peer-reviewed scholarly journal.

3. Articles

[Developing Open Access Journals: A practical guide](#) (2008), an article authored by David J. Solomon, is an abridged version of the original book published by Chandos Publishing, Oxford, England.

[Scholarly journal publishing standards, policies and guidelines](#) (2021) is an article by Miriam Wanjiku Ndungu offering an overview of what you need to consider when starting a journal.

[Reasons to Launch a Journal](#) (2022), by John Warren, is an in-depth look at why one journal was started.

[Publishing with Open Journal Systems \(OJS\): A Librarian's Perspective](#) (2020), by Miriam Wanjiku Ndungu, lays the context of online hosting of university sponsored journals in Kenya and gives a background of Online Journals Systems.

4. Courses

The [Library Publishing Curriculum](#) (LPC) is a suite of synchronous and asynchronous professional development offerings for librarians that are open and free under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license for anyone to offer or adapt. This dynamic, extensible curriculum is intended to empower librarians to meet local demands to launch and/or enhance scholarly publishing activities. It is published by the Library Publishing Coalition.

[Publishing Workflow Courses](#) is a series of guidelines offered by the PKP School for editors, peer reviewers, and writers.

5. Newsletters

[The Geyser](#) is a newsletter devoted to analyzing, discussing, and interpreting key information and updates about publishing, information purveyance, technology, commerce, and strategy.

[The Brief](#) is a monthly newsletter covering professional and scholarly communication published by Clarke & Esposito.

[Journalology](#) is a newsletter that helps editors and publishing professionals keep up to date with scholarly publishing, and guides them on how to build influential scholarly journals.

6. Podcasts

[Grammar Girl](#) is a podcast with 924 episodes as of April 2023 that has been named one of Writer's Digest's 101 best websites for writers multiple times.

7. Bibliographic databases

The [Scientific Electronic Library Online](#) (SCIELO) is a bibliographic database, digital library, and cooperative electronic publishing model of open access journals. SciELO was created to meet the scientific communication needs of developing countries and provides an efficient way to increase visibility and access to scientific literature.

8. Style Guides

[Scientific Style and Format: The CBE Manual for Authors, Editors, and Publishers](#) (6th edition) is a book published in 1995 by Cambridge University Press that is currently out of print. It is a detailed and authoritative manual recommending both general and scientific publication styles and formats for journals, books, and other forms of publication.

The [Chicago Manual of Style Online](#) (CMOS or TCM or CMS or Chicago) is the online version of the style guide for American English published since 1906 by the University of Chicago Press. Its 17 editions have prescribed writing and citation styles widely used in publishing.

The [American Psychological Association \(APA\) style guide](#) is a free online style guide to the APA citation and academic writing style.

The [New Oxford Dictionary for Writers and Editors](#) is a book published by Oxford University Press in 2014 that is a general writing style guide and endorsed by the Society for Editors and Proofreaders.

The [AMA Manual of Style: A Guide for Authors and Editors](#) (11th edition) is the style guide of the American Medical Association and is most recently published by Oxford University Press.

[Scientific English: A Guide for Scientists and Other Professionals](#) (2011) and [How to Write and Publish a Scientific Paper](#) (2011) are books published by Robert A. Day.

9. Societies

The [Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association](#) (OASPA) represents a diverse community of organizations engaged in open scholarship. Members include both individuals and organizations.

The [Society for Scholarly Publishing](#) (SSP) is a nonprofit organization formed to promote and advance communication among all sectors of the scholarly publication community through networking, information dissemination, and facilitation of new developments in the field.

The [Council of Science Editors](#) (CSE) is an international membership organization for editorial professionals publishing in the sciences.

The [Coalition for Diversity and Inclusion in Scholarly Communications](#) (C4DISC) was formed to discuss and address issues of diversity and inclusion within the Scholarly Communications industry.

The [Scholarly Kitchen](#) is a moderated and independent blog on Scholarly Publishing published by the Society for Scholarly Publishing (SSP).

The [Turkish Academic Network and Information Center](#)'s (ULAKBIM) main objectives have been set as operating a high speed computer network enabling interaction within the research and education elements of the national innovation system, and providing information technology and library and information services to the research community in Turkey.

The [World Association of Medical Editors](#) (WAME) is a nonprofit voluntary association of editors of peer-reviewed medical journals from countries throughout the world who seek to foster international cooperation among and education of medical journal editors.

The [Brazilian Association of Science Editors](#) (ABEC Brasil) is a Brazilian nonprofit organization founded in 1985, and dedicated to the advancement of publication of scientific journals. As of April 2023 the website is available only in Portuguese.

The [Croatian Association for Scholarly Communication](#)'s (ZNAK) aim is to promote scholarly communication, especially the activities of Croatian scientific and professional journals, and publications that promote science to the general public.

The [European Association of Science Editors](#) (EASE) is an international community of editors from diverse backgrounds, linguistic traditions and professional experience who share a passion for science and scholarly communication, editing and publishing.

The [Committee on Publication Ethics](#) (COPE) is committed to educating and supporting editors, publishers, universities, research institutes, and all those involved in publication ethics. COPE aims to move the culture of publishing towards one where ethical practices become a normal part of the culture itself.

The [International Committee of Medical Journal Editors](#) (ICMJE) is a small working group of general medical journal editors whose participants meet annually and fund their own work on the Recommendations for the Conduct, Reporting, Editing and Publication of Scholarly Work in Medical Journals.

[Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology](#) (STROBE) stands for an international, collaborative initiative of epidemiologists, methodologists, statisticians, researchers and journal editors involved in the conduct and dissemination of observational studies, with the common aim of STrengthening the Reporting of OBservational studies in Epidemiology.

[Library Publishing Coalition](#) (LPC) extends the impact and sustainability of library publishing and open scholarship by providing a professional forum for developing best practices and shared expertise.

[Association of University Presses](#) (AUPresses) advances the essential role of a global community of publishers whose mission is to ensure academic excellence and cultivate knowledge.

[Mediterranean Editors & Translators](#) (MET) is an association of language professionals who work mainly into or with English. Members include both in-house and freelance language professionals, individuals and businesses; they work with institutions, governments, corporations and NGOs.